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Progressing Research on Basic Education

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Abstract

This study explored the implementation of Division Research Program PROBE (Progressing Research On Basic Education) on its third and last year and investigated the utilization of contextualized action research guidebook. A quantitative research method employing descriptive approach was utilized in the study. Participants were research leaders in the division which were selected purposively. Results showed that in terms of development ($M=3.850$, $SD=0.499$) and utilization ($M=3.650$, $SD=0.421$) of contextualized action research guidebook, majority of participants agreed that it was “highly desirable”. Moreover, Participants perceived that the material is “highly acceptable” in terms of content ($M=3.950$, $SD=0.480$), usability ($M=3.850$, $SD=0.455$), and quality ($M=3.750$, $SD=0.409$). Lastly, in its effectiveness ($M=3.800$, $SD=0.137$), participants agreed that the contextualized action research guidebook is “highly effective”. There were limitations in the conduct of the study such as difficulty understanding technical terminologies and crafting research at their own pace. Nonetheless, participants realized the significance of the implementation of the Division Research Program and the use of contextualized action research guidebook towards easier and more accessible process of crafting action research.

Keywords: *contextualized action research guidebook, research culture, synergy, innovation, and collaboration*

Introduction

In accordance with Republic Act 9155 otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, this mandates that the Department of Education enact policies and mechanisms through which the delivery of quality basic education may be continuously improved. With this, SDO-Biñan City upholds the environment of evidence-based decision-making and policy formulation activities supported by research studies (DO No. 13, s. 2015). Further, within five (5) years of operation, SDO-Biñan City is continuously gearing towards the promotion of culture of research. The division participated in different research initiatives of the Regional Office since 2017. However, based on the division’s Annual Accomplishment Report (AAR) of fiscal year 2020, there were 45 submitted research proposals, but only 17 were aligned with the new normal, four (4) of which were approved by Basic Education Research Fund (BERF) which is 23.5% of the total submission. Despite the volume of trainings and research initiatives in the division, the turn-out of crafted research is significantly lower than target. Based on survey, focus group discussion and results of needs assessment, many teaching and non-teaching personnel in the division were interested to craft action research but they lack significant information, idea, and pre-requisite skills on how to start and accomplish one.

This is an emerging concern as we gear towards the promotion of the culture of research in the division as basis of evidence-based decision-making and policy formulation. Hence, this study leans towards one of the principles where the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan stands on. Under section 3 (e) of D.O. No. 12, s. 2020, to link and bridge BE-LCP to DepEd’s pivot to quality and into the future of education, under the framework of Sulong Edukalidad and Futures Thinking in Education. Moreover, this is anchored on the Region IV-A CALABARZON’s enhanced BE-LCP dimension relative to Focus on Learning-Ensuring Quality of Teaching and Learning Process, which provides standard learning and development programs for teachers.

Despite the volume of trainings and research initiatives in the division, the turn-out of crafted research is significantly lower than the target. This is where the idea of PROBE (Progressing Research On Basic Education) Revitalizing the Research Culture in the New Normal stands on. It is a 3-year research program launched in the division, catering to teacher-researchers and all research enthusiasts, that provided technical inputs, strategies, and mechanics on the conduct of research. Furthermore, it enhanced synergy, collaboration, and revitalized the culture of research in the Division of Biñan City.

During the Implementation of PROBE in the year 2020-2021, there is a significant increase in the accomplished and completed research in the division. There were 58 completed studies covering diverse types of categories such as teaching and learning, governance, and child protection comprising 73.42% accomplishment rate with 1 research being granted under the Basic Education Research Fund (BERF). This proved that PROBE is an effective research program launched in the division. This year is the third and last year of its implementation to continue all its projects and activities. Consequently, another project was launched this year. A Contextualized Research Guidebook was developed and utilized to further help researchers in crafting their own research to be utilized in the whole division.

The results of the study served as basis on the use of Contextualized Research Guidebook in crafting research in the division. This further improved the research skills of researchers and sustained the research culture in the division.

Methodology

The study utilized descriptive quantitative research method. Descriptive statistics to analyze the quantitative data were gathered from

the 4-point Likert scale questionnaire crafted by the researcher and validated by experts to reveal the effectiveness of the project in terms of the set parameters. The collected data was analyzed and reported using tables. Quantitative data was reported and analyzed using the results of the survey questionnaire to determine the acceptability of participants in the contextualized action research guidebook.

The idea of the study is shown in the framework below:

The diagram above shows the Input-Process-Output model of the study. The Input shows the problems to be answered in the study. The Process includes the intervention made by the researcher to answer the problems posted, the PROBE (Progressing Research On Basic Education). This program aims to enhance collaboration, uphold synergy, and promote the culture of research in the division of Biñan City through a series of projects and activities. These include three (3) stages which developed the different domains of the participants, namely: Stage 1: i-CREATE (Capacitating Research Enthusiasts through Advanced Training and Engagement) which advanced the cognitive domain; Stage 2: i-CRAFT (Intensifying Collaboration through Research Advancement Fostering Transformation) which developed the affective domain; and Stage 3: i-STAR (Intensified Skills Training on Action Research) which enhanced the psychomotor domain and writing skills of the participants. Moreover, the output showed the expected outcome of the study which is synergy, collaboration, and enhanced culture of research in SDO-Biñan City and crafted research of participants.

The study highlighted the use of Contextualized Research Guidebook. This material provided step-by-step procedure on how to craft research starting from problem identification up to presentation and dissemination of results in accordance with the Research Management Guidelines (RMG).

The study started with the crafting and validation of different tools and instruments to be utilized in the study. Participants were identified to undergo survey and interview. After the data gathering procedure, all data was treated accordingly. Analysis and crafting of research summary were conducted. Lastly, crafting of the final paper including the results and recommendations.

To adhere with ethical considerations and standards, all participants were informed of the study. Matters about Data Privacy were elaborated and clarified, with proper adherence to RA 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. An informed consent was given to the participants prior to the conduct of the study. They were informed that they may withdraw their participation in the study if they wish to do so. Anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were considered accordingly.

Results and Discussion

Most of the participants agreed that the contextualized action research guidebook is “highly desirable” in terms of development with a mean score of 3.850 and standards deviation of 0.499, and utilization with a mean score of 3.650 and standard deviation of 0.421. This revealed that the participants see the necessity of a contextualized action research guidebook and it aids as they craft their own research.

The participants ascertain the said material is “highly acceptable” in terms of content ($M=3.950$, $SD=0.480$), usability ($M=3.850$, $SD=0.455$), and quality ($M=3.750$, $SD=0.409$). This means that the contextualized action research guidebook matches the needs of the participants.

A mean score of 3.800 and standard deviation of 0.137 was obtained int in terms of effectiveness, which means that the participants agreed that the contextualized action research guidebook is “highly effective”. This implied that the participants were guided and were able to craft their action research using the material. Moreover, it yielded positive results in the creation of research initiatives. There was a notable increase in the completed research in the Division.

Conclusions

PROBE (Progressing Research On Basic Education) is an effective intervention program in revitalizing the research culture to uphold synergy and collaboration in the division, despite the challenges experienced. Furthermore, the use of contextualized action research guidebook is deemed helpful and was able to assist all participants to successfully accomplish their own research.

Hence, the following conclusions were drawn:

Based on the results of the survey, the researcher-made contextualized action research guidebook was highly desirable in terms of development and utilization.

In terms of content, usability, and quality, the material is said to be highly acceptable. These factors are considered significant in the acceptability of the guidebook since it provides information to the participants in crafting their own research. These are considered to ensure that the participants benefited from the use of the guidebook. Also, these items may be further improved to increase their effectiveness for future users.

In terms of effectiveness the material is highly effective. It proved that the contextualized action research guidebook assisted the participants as they craft their own research. All the participants were able to craft their research. Moreover, there was a significant increase in the amount of completed research in the Division. This is a very significant indicator to measure the success of the program and also to gauge the level of research culture in the division. Not only that the participants were able to write a research proposal, but more participants were able to successfully complete their research. This implied a success both for the program and of the researchers themselves.

Based on the salient findings of the study, the following are recommended:

The Division Research Program PROBE (Progressing Research On Basic Education) may be sustained, particularly in promoting different innovation in helping researchers in crafting their own research. The use of contextualized action research guidebook is deemed to be highly acceptable and highly effective; it may further be improved and may be used to bigger population to widen its impact. The contextualized action research guidebook may be submitted to experts for further quality control measures and future publication.

The participants experienced different challenges such as technical writing challenges. One participant mentioned:

“ang pinaka-challenge lang po talaga sa akin ay yung mag-isip ako on my own, since I have no, uhmm, knowledgeable well, or I’m not, hindi po talaga ako knowledgeable sa research, nahihirapan ako pag ako na po ang nagco-construct.”

This implied that the participants lack technical writing skills prior to utilization of the guidebook. However, after the utilization of the material they were able to overcome challenges like this. One participant mentioned:

“based sa experience ko Sir, modesty aside, I feel more relaxed in crafting my action research, because of the contextualized guidebook. Parang thesis ang level nya para sa akin, pero since guided ako, andun na din ang example, at kapag may tanong ako, babalikan ko lang sya tapos sasagutin ka din nya eh.”

Since, it was proven effective specific procedure may be implemented to further widen the impact of the program such as (1) division-wide implementation of the program; (2) quality assurance and validation of the contextualized guidebook; (3) continuation and sustainability of the program; and (4) inclusion of the program in the Division Education Development Plan for Planning and Research.

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